

IMPROVING SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCY OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Personal development is a powerful tool to reach a well-defined and healthy sense of self as teachers, i.a, self-concept enhancement, which can result in positive self-esteem and self-confidence. Besides, it enables teachers to recognize, understand and manage their emotions thereby having good intrapersonal skills and the article also reflected on these.

Keywords: professional practice, skills, motivation, solving problems, lose control.

INTRODUCTION

Professional development, also referred to as professional learning by teachers already engaged in professional practice and is the process of developing the necessary knowledge-base, skills teachers require to carry out their role effectively.

This does not only involve learning new theoretical teaching ideas and suggestions but also trying them out and learning how to make them more effective within their teaching contexts. Teachers’ ongoing reflection, evaluation, analysis of their own practices are necessary elements of their professional development as these can support them construct new teaching theories and improve more their performances (learning-by-doing approach as put forward by Whitford, 1994).

METHODS

Schools as educational organizations want their human resources to be able to contribute as much as possible to the school. Human resources in carrying out their duties still always face problems that cannot be solved by their selves. It happens because the ability of human resources has not met school expectations. The learning process at school is considered as a routine repetition and delivery of knowledge

content that does not force students to develop creativity, taste, initiative, work, and social care. Primary school developing students' social skills such as taking turns, listening, understanding and communicating the intended meaning is deemed essential in today's education. But, are teachers prepared for this task? Do they possess the social skills to interact effectively with those around them?

It seems that much more focus is given to students' social skills development whereas less attention is devoted to primary school teachers' social development. The latter refers to developing the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes that enable teachers to relate to others effectively and to contribute positively to their community.

Indeed, being critical, reflective on teaching experiences and motivated to bring change and improvement are essential for teachers' professional development. Today's teachers should be experts in their work, i.e., planning their lessons, communicating, managing and accessing the activities of the teaching-learning process more effectively, and meanwhile adaptive, i.e., being flexible to different students' needs and preferences.

RESULTS

Primary class teacher development occurs when these aspects of development are occurring: personal, professional and social development. This is because teacher development is a learning process, so emotions have a say on how the brain functions; positive emotions (like motivation) boost engagement in learning. Quality knowledge understanding are of utmost importance to learning (cognition).

Teacher training aims to help teachers learn the necessary pedagogical knowledge and skills. More particularly, it is mostly concerned with the "How". For instance, how to use a particular digital tool and integrate it into a given lesson, how to teach mixed-ability classes, how to flip the classroom, etc.

According to the scientist O.Musurmonova, professional competence is the ability of a teacher to turn his profession into a tool for the development of the child's personality, taking into account the restrictions and guidelines imposed on the educational process by the requirements of pedagogical norms. According to N.Muslimov, the concept of "pedagogical competence" includes knowledge, skills, abilities, methods and ways to implement them in activity, communication, personal development, as well as activity, communicative and social competencies.

Personal development or self-development refers to possessing personal strengths and characteristics that aid teachers define and make sense of their teaching practice and of themselves as individuals. This is through developing the necessary life skills that can help them grow in and outside their profession.

DISCUSSION

There is a range of life skills that assist teachers in coping with the challenges of everyday living. Getting organized, solving problems, engaging, caring about students are among the key life skills that teachers need in the profession. Because teachers' professional role can be affected by their personal-life factors, they need to develop certain life skills related to their personal life. These can include balancing their professional, personal lives and coping with family pressure, stress and negative emotions (like anger, sadness, etc.), making effective decisions concerning their health, etc.

These building blocks of primary class teacher development are interrelated, i.e., each development's aspect depends on the other aspects. To illustrate, a teacher who can't manage his emotions or self-regulate (not personally developed) is not likely to control or manage effectively his classroom and thus interact effectively with his students (cannot develop professionally and socially). When feeling angry he will burn out, lose control, treat badly and he may even forget the lesson plan. These types of development should be the intended outcome of any teacher development intention or programme.

CONCLUSION

Primary class teacher development is an evolving learning process. This learning process is ongoing and endless. Even if a teacher has achieved certain development, he still needs to learn along with his whole life and career.

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